

MPHYS PROJECT REPORT (SEMESTER 2)

An Exploration of Bayesian Techniques in Application to the Matrix Element Method and $t\bar{t}h$ Processes

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Abstract

Bayesian inference is a technique used to statistically sample from the “posterior” probability distribution of unknown parameters in a model. This was successfully applied to the reconstruction of neutrino momenta in $t\bar{t}h$ events by using the Matrix Element Method to define a likelihood function for use in an inference algorithm known as nested sampling. Many implementations of nested sampling were explored; POLYCHORD and Nestle performed the best in application to this problem. A strong correlation between reconstructed neutrino momenta and the momentum values at truth level was found when analysing simulated signal data at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. Moreover, this correlation was significantly worse when the permutation of outgoing b -jets from top quark decay were switched. Extensions to reduce repeated evaluations of the likelihood function – a key feature of nested sampling that incurs a high computational load due to the nature of calculating scattering cross-sections – are detailed for future work.

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1 Introduction

The Matrix Element Method (MEM) is a technique used to calculate the probability density function (pdf) of a scattering process based upon the physics behind that process. The strength of the MEM is that one can compute the pdf through calculation of a single integral, which involves the quantum mechanical matrix element of the scattering matrix S . The MEM has previously been used in application to $t\bar{t}h$, which was the basis for this project [1, 2].

The high-level goal of this project is full event reconstruction in events with a $t\bar{t}h$ vertex and dileptonic final state. This would allow us to measure accurately the top quark Yukawa coupling, which could give an indication of the scale of new physics [3]. In addition, one could explore the properties of the Higgs boson. To achieve full reconstruction, we need to somehow reconstruct the momentum of the two produced neutrinos in each event, which are only able to be inferred physically through missing transverse momentum p_T^{miss} . In order to do this, we turned to a statistical technique known as Bayesian inference (BI).

BI allows for the stochastic determination of unknown parameters in a model through sampling of the “posterior” distribution of the parameters given the data set. In addition, BI has the ability to calculate the so-called “evidence” for that configuration of parameters. If one has prior information about the distribution of these parameters (and indeed of any sub-parameters of these parameters), BI methods serve to update those prior beliefs by taking them into account when performing inference.

Through mapping the MEM to a Bayesian problem, this report discusses successful inference using a technique called Nested Sampling [4], and explores computational implementations suited to the problem.

My contributions to this project over its duration include:

- Development of a version of the MEM to coalesce with the DIAMONDS implementation of nested sampling in C++, as well as performing analysis and plotting results.
- Adapting a new Python-based code structure to perform nested sampling with a package called POLYCHORD, and production of code to analyse and process results.
- Installing and testing additional implementations of nested sampling to find the best method suited to this problem.
- Researching methods to reduce computation time using Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques.

Throughout this report, all logarithms are given in base e , and natural units are used.

2 Background

This section begins by introducing the physical processes studied in this project and the justification as to why this is an interesting problem, including an outline of the Matrix Element Method. The ATLAS detector is also briefly discussed, along with the details of the simulated data used.

2.1 Physics

2.1.1 $t\bar{t}h$ processes

The top quark is the heaviest known elementary particle, discovered in 1995 by the CDF and DØ experiments at the Tevatron [5, 6]. The top quark is unique amongst the quarks in that its lifetime ($\approx 5 \times 10^{-25}$ s) is too short to form bound states such as baryons and mesons. It decays to b quarks almost exclusively.

A boson was discovered in 2012 by the ATLAS collaboration with mass 126.0 ± 0.8 GeV with a significance of 5.9σ . This is widely believed to correspond to the Higgs boson (h) predicted by the Standard Model of particle physics (SM) [7]. The dominant decay mode of the Higgs to two b quarks ($h \rightarrow b\bar{b}$) has a branching ratio of 57.7% [8], which is the decay considered throughout this report.

Figure 1: The Feynman diagram for two gluons producing $t\bar{t}$ pairs, which combine to form a $t\bar{t}h$ vertex. This is an example signal event.

Figure 2: The Feynman diagram for two gluons producing $t\bar{t}$ pairs, but in contrast to Figure 1, form a vertex with another gluon. This is an example background event.

This project concerns signal processes with a $t\bar{t}h$ vertex, i.e. one where a top and an anti-top quark together produce a Higgs boson. An example Feynman diagram is shown in Figure 1. Processes that create the same final state but don't include a $t\bar{t}h$ vertex, known collectively as $t\bar{t}b\bar{b}$, are considered background events, an example of which is shown in Figure 2. The coupling for a $t\bar{t}h$ vertex is known as the top quark Yukawa coupling y_t , which is predicted by the SM. Deviations from the predicted value could indicate the scale to which “new” physics contributes to this coupling, making a precision measurement of y_t an important test of the SM.

2.1.2 The Matrix Element Method (MEM)

The main result from the MEM is summarised here – a corresponding theoretical underpinning can be found in [9].

Using a probabilistic approach in addition to quantum mechanical and kinematic considerations, the probability density function $f(\cdot)$ of the set of kinematics P given model & detector parameters α & β for $A + B \rightarrow 1 + 2 + \dots + N$ scattering takes the form

$$\underbrace{f_a(P|\alpha, \beta)}_{\text{Probability density } f^n} = \underbrace{\frac{(2\pi)^4}{\sigma_a(\alpha)}}_{\text{Normalisation}} \int \underbrace{\frac{1}{\mathcal{F}}}_{\text{Flux factor}} \underbrace{\mathcal{M}(K|\alpha)}_{\text{Matrix element}} \underbrace{W(P|K, \beta)}_{\text{Transfer } f^n\text{s}} \underbrace{d\Phi_N}_{\text{Kinematics}} \underbrace{\zeta(x_2, Q^2)}_{\text{PDFs}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{F} = 4\sqrt{(p_A \cdot p_B)^2 - m_A^2 m_B^2}$ is the Lorentz-invariant flux factor (p_i and m_i are the four-momentum and mass of particle i respectively), $\mathcal{M}(K|\alpha) = |T_{fi}|^2 \prod_j 2E_j$ is the Lorentz invariant matrix element [10], $\zeta(x_2, Q^2)$ represents the parton distribution function contributions, $d\Phi_N$ is the phase space element of the $A + B \rightarrow 1 + 2 + \dots + N$ process, and $W(P|K, \beta)$ are the transfer functions that give probability distributions for the energies of the particles, incorporating detector effects. This is the strength of the MEM — through a numerical calculation of an integral given detector observables, we automatically encode the physics of the process into any probabilistic inference we may do.

For a candidate signal event with the required final state, we don't know the true permutation of the outgoing b -jets, so there are additional levels of uncertainty that need to be accounted for. This is done by summing the contributions for each permutation for the final calculation.

2.2 Approximations

In order to reduce the degrees of freedom in the problem to make it computationally feasible, a number of approximations are made:

- Both charged leptons are perfectly reconstructed.
- b -jets have exact mass & direction reconstruction.
- Incoming partons have zero transverse momentum.
- If a particle has a mass less than that of the b quark, that mass is neglected.
- Energy & momentum are exactly conserved.
- All leptons are electron flavour.

Using these, the only free parameters left in the MEM integral are the b -jet energies, and the neutrino three-momenta. Since we can reconstruct any two of the components of the three-momenta of the neutrino or the anti-neutrino using p_t^{miss} , these only present four degrees of freedom, leaving a total of eight.

2.3 ATLAS detector

ATLAS (A Toroidal LHC ApparatuS) [11] is an experiment at the LHC designed to investigate proton-proton collisions, with focuses on searching for beyond SM physics & testing the SM. The ATLAS coordinate system has the z -axis in the longitudinal (beam pipe) direction, with the xy -plane forming the transverse plane. The structure of the detector is as follows, radially outward from the beam pipe:

- Systems to precisely track and measure particles (inner detector/trackers),
- Electromagnetic & hadronic calorimeters that measure signatures of charged particles through observing energy losses (ECAL/HCAL),
- Dedicated trackers to observe muons via observing their curvature through strong magnetic fields (muon chambers).

Quarks are observed in the detector as collimated jets of particles that arise due to hadronisation, which incur uncertainty. Neutrinos are only able to be inferred through the missing transverse momentum p_t^{miss} in events.

2.4 Event generation

It was found early on in the development of this project that the data set we were using was mistakenly generated at $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV due to default settings made before the LHC upgrade not being adjusted. Signal and background events at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV were generated using MadGraph5_aMC@NLO with the commands

- generate p p > t t~ h, t > b e+ ve, t~ > b~ e- ve~, h > b b~ (signal)

- generate $p > t \sim b \sim$, $t > b \text{ e}^+ \text{ ve}$, $t \sim b \sim \text{e}^- \text{ ve}$ (background).

3 Bayesian Inference

3.1 Theory

Bayesian inference (BI) is completely based upon Bayes' theorem, which states that for probability distribution $\pi(\cdot)$, data \mathbf{x} , and model parameters $\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n\}$,

$$\pi(\theta|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\pi(\mathbf{x}|\theta)\pi(\theta)}{\pi(\mathbf{x})} \quad (2)$$

The distributions each have their own special name: $\pi(\theta|\mathbf{x})$ is the joint **posterior** distribution of the parameters θ , $\pi(\mathbf{x}|\theta)$ is known as the **likelihood** $\mathcal{L}(\theta|\mathbf{x})$, $\pi(\theta)$ is the product of the individual distributions $\pi(\theta_i)$ which are the **prior** distributions for each parameter, and the normalising factor $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ is the Bayesian **evidence** Z , which is obtained by marginalising the unknown parameters

$$Z = \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{L}(\theta|\mathbf{x}) \times \pi(\theta) d\theta \quad (3)$$

over parameter domain Ω . Often, Bayesian computation only requires proportionality with respect to the parameters, so it's common to just think of the equation

$$\text{Posterior} \propto \text{Likelihood} \times \text{Priors} \quad (4)$$

as the defining equation of BI, though from the expression for the evidence above, one can see Z is an important indicator of the average likelihood, which is neglected in some approaches.

BI methods usually have the goal of calculating Z and sampling from the posterior. In application to *tth*, the former can be used as a way to discriminate between signal and background events, and also between permutations of the outgoing *b*-jets, whether as the latter can be used to reconstruct the neutrino momenta, as they are unknown parameters of the model.

The posterior distribution of interest is that of the neutrino momenta and *b*-jet energies given the detector observables. One can map the relevant quantities from particle physics to their appropriate Bayesian counterparts in order to sample from this posterior. Using the MEM, we already have our likelihood function – the MEM integrand serves as exactly the distribution of the kinematic data given the unknown model parameters. Now, strictly speaking, one should consider the transfer functions as *prior* distributions on the *b*-jet energies, however in practice, they form part of the MEM integrand, so they can be implemented as part of the likelihood as a result.

The problem then remains to select a suitable candidate method to perform this inference.

3.2 Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)

The most-used technique to perform BI is known as Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC); the two are fairly synonymous in literature. These methods use a Markov chain with a stationary distribution of the posterior, meaning one can simply iterate in moving the current position in the chain towards the stationary state in order to produce samples from the posterior. Examples of MCMC methods include Gibbs sampling, random walk Metropolis, and the relatively new Hamiltonian Monte Carlo.

This approach is useful for parameter estimation, however can run into some problems. For instance, many MCMC algorithms struggle with the presence of multiple modes in the posterior distribution, which we know our neutrinos will have based on previous work [9]. In addition, MCMC methods neglect calculating evidences, so they are unable to average over the prior, and instead just explore the posterior, which doesn't give any information about how likely your sample is to be correct [12].

Figure 3: An illustration of how Nested Sampling constrains the likelihood for each set of points sampled consecutively in regions defined by iso-likelihood contours with likelihoods L_i .

3.3 Nested Sampling

In 2006, John Skilling published a paper entitled “Nested Sampling for General Bayesian Computation” [4], which proposed an alternative to MCMC techniques that took into account evidences. The algorithm works like so:

```

draw a set of  $n$  samples  $S_0$  for each parameter  $j$  from their respective priors  $\pi(\theta_j)$ 
 $i = 0$ 
while !(stopping condition) do
    calculate  $\mathcal{L}(S_i|\text{data})$ 
    sample new points  $S^*$  for each parameter  $j$  from their respective priors  $\pi(\theta_j)$ .
    calculate  $\mathcal{L}(S^*|\text{data})$ 
    if  $\mathcal{L}(S_i|\text{data}) < \mathcal{L}(S^*|\text{data})$  then
         $S_{i+1} = S^*$ 
    else
         $S_{i+1} = S_i$ 
    end if
     $i = i + 1$ 
end while
calculate weights  $w \propto$  posterior mass for samples  $S$ 
calculate evidence  $Z = \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{L}(\theta|\mathbf{x}) \times \pi(\theta) d\theta$ 
return  $S, w, Z$ 

```

This procedure is known as **nested sampling** (NS). It works by iteratively shrinking the sample likelihood contours in the parameter space of interest in order to sample points around areas of high posterior density. An illustration of this is shown in Figure 3. The samples at the current iteration are the “live” points, whilst the rejected samples are conversely known as “dead” points. The output from the algorithm is a weighted set of posterior samples for each parameter using both the live and the dead points, along with the corresponding evidence value for the run as a whole. The weight of a sample point is proportional to its share of the posterior mass. At each iteration of the algorithm, the likelihood contour volume decreases like $\approx \frac{1}{n}$, meaning that the posterior mode(s) is(are) reached exponentially quicker with each iteration [12].

NS calculates evidences by switching integration variable from the parameters $d\theta$ to the so-called **prior mass** $\pi(\theta) d\theta = dX$. This is termed as such due to the integral $\int_{\mathcal{L}(\theta|\mathbf{x}) < \mathcal{L}_i} X dX$ resulting in the fraction of the prior enclosed by the iso-likelihood contour \mathcal{L}_i . If one assigns a value of prior mass for each sample, then due to the nature of the algorithm, $\mathcal{L}(X)$ becomes a monotonic function of X by construction, as shown in Figure 4. One can then use simple tools such as Simpson’s rule to perform the integration [13].

Figure 4: A plot taken from [12] highlighting the monotonic nature of $\mathcal{L}(X)$ with subsequent values of X_i and likelihood contours \mathcal{L}_i .

4 Project Implementations

NS has a wide variety of implementations in many different coding languages. Since our likelihood function is very computationally demanding and multi-modal, multiple techniques to perform NS were explored that would overcome these issues, and their corresponding implementations in code adapted to incorporate the matrix element calculations and other relevant physics.

Throughout this section, ν_i ; $i \in \{x, y, z\}$ is used to refer to the i th component of the three-momentum of the neutrino (or anti-neutrino $\bar{\nu}$). All analyses in this section were performed at truth level. The parameterisation of the neutrino momenta used for these implementations is the three-momentum of the neutrino, and the z momentum of the anti-neutrino, as we can reconstruct the rest through kinematic considerations.

4.1 DIAMONDS

4.1.1 Theory

DIAMONDS is an implementation of NS based on a method known as simultaneous ellipsoidal sampling (SES) [14, 15]. SES works by performing an initial clustering of the samples using a method known as X-means clustering [16], then iteratively constraining likelihood contours for each cluster simultaneously. This implementation of NS was attractive, since SES is very good at distinguishing multiple posterior modes. Moreover, it is entirely C++-based, meaning a large speed improvement over the same implementation with interpreted languages (e.g. Python) would be expected. Another strength of DIAMONDS is that it operates using an object-oriented class-based structure, allowing for flexible changes in the implementations of the likelihood & priors, which proved useful when trying to incorporate the existing code structure.

4.1.2 Results

This was the first attempt to incorporate the full MEM integrand into NS, so some preliminary groundwork needed to be done. Efforts in the previous semester yielded a GPU-ready version of code to calculate the MEM integrand. The software setup involves Python scripts to execute processes on the GPU, which are written in CUDA C. The parton distribution functions are calculated by bilinear interpolation from CT10 data sets [17]. The matrix elements are calculated using a modified version of HELAS (HELicity Amplitude Subroutines), which is a suite of functions that compute arbitrary tree-level helicity amplitudes [18].

Figure 5: Histogram of the weighted posterior sample for the energy of the b -jet coming from the anti-top quark when integrating over the four b -jet energies, produced with R.

This version of the MEM calculations was trans-coded from CUDA C into C++ over a couple of weeks, and then adapted to fit the structure of DIAMONDS. This idea of modular structure was the starting point for a future redevelopment of the code. Installing DIAMONDS itself proved much more difficult than anticipated, as problems arose from using CERN external library files and compilers in conjunction with a local installation. Eventually, the install was successful, and analysis was performed.

The first test was to see how well the program did when integrating over just the four b -energies with Gaussian priors about their truth-level values in the simulated data. Analysis was performed on the first event of the ATLAS simulated data with $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV with 100 live points, and the true permutation for outgoing b -jets was used. Here, the algorithm performed well as expected – a histogram of the weighted samples for the energy of the b -jet coming from the anti-top quark is shown in Figure 5 as an example.

After this, integrating over the neutrinos in addition with uniform priors was carried out, which posed some problems. Even with the Gaussian priors on the b -energies, the posterior distributions for the momenta were offset from the true values to various degrees. The relevant plots are shown in Figure 6, with values at truth level plotted as vertical grey lines.

At this point, the C++ implementation of the MEM code was systematically debugged, as it was feared that there may either have been an error in the initial code, or perhaps something was lost in translation from CUDA. The only thing that seemed to be causing problems was the parton distribution function code; those contributions were suppressed, and analysis resumed. Results improved, but the modes still didn't match up satisfactorily to the true values for that event, evidenced in Figure 7, which shows the two best plots for that run.

After many weeks spent debugging the DIAMONDS code to no avail, the approach was abandoned in favour of a restructured version of the code that was being developed in Python alongside this analysis. This led to alternative methods of NS being sought out that were implemented in Python.

4.2 Nestle

4.2.1 Theory

Nestle is a pure Python implementation of NS, which can be found at [19]. It incorporates a number of methods; `classic` mode uses an algorithm close to Skilling's original with a MCMC walk, `single` performs NS by trying to contain the whole iso-likelihood region in a single ellipsoid, and `multi` uses an approach found in the MULTINEST package that uses multiple ellipsoids to contain the iso-likelihood region [20]. The `classic` mode is used in the following analysis.

Figure 6: Plots of output from DIAMONDS analysis of the first event of the $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV data set. Gaussian priors of width 2 GeV about the true value of each b -jet are used. Values at truth level are plotted as vertical grey lines. Produced with R. Note that plotting style differs slightly from the previous plot due to a difference in familiarity with the plotting package over time.

Figure 7: Plots of output from DIAMONDS analysis of the first event of the $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV data set. Gaussian priors of width 2 GeV about the true value of each b -jet are used. Parton distribution function contributions to the likelihood are suppressed. Produced with R.

Nestle uses what’s known as a *prior transform*, which allows sampling to be performed in $(0,1)$ and then be mapped back to the original range of values. Since NS starts by sampling in the whole parameter space – which is impossible without restricting the range of your parameters in some way – it is very convenient to have the parameter space naturally be restricted to $(0,1)$. This yields the ability to easily sample priors such as the normal distribution which extend to $(-\infty, \infty)$ [19]. The approach taken here is to not specify the form of the transform within Nestle, and instead just convert the outputted samples $u \in (0,1)$ straight to physical momentum. Samples $u \in (0,1)$ are the output from the algorithm in this case, with the prior transform mapping these back to the original range.

The chosen transform from $(0,1)$ to $(-\infty, \infty)$ is termed as a “gradient doubling” transform, which takes the form

$$z = \frac{a(2u + 1)}{1 - (2u + 1)^2} \quad \text{for } u \in (0,1), z \in (-\infty, \infty), a \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (5)$$

Here, a plays the role of a scale factor for each parameter, which is dependent on the kinematics of the problem in this case. It will be specified in future plots whether the variable being plotted is the unit parameter or the actual physical momentum values.

4.2.2 Code Restructuring[†]

Work was done using MadGraph to generate new leading order matrix element calculators suited to our problem. To incorporate these into the MEM, a class-based modular code structure with standardised interface between matrix elements, parton distribution functions, transfer functions, and input variable transformations was developed in Python, which makes Nestle a great option for NS.

An additional feature of this is the introduction of a “Higgs parameter” that takes into account both the energies of the b -jets produced by the Higgs boson in signal events, which subsequently reduces the degrees of freedom in our problem to seven. More details on this can be found in [9, 21].

All analyses after this section were performed with this modified structure on $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV sets of signal and background data generated with MadGraph tools.

4.2.3 Results[†]

Considerable progress was made with Nestle over the duration of the project, with only a few results summarised here. Analysis was performed over all 10000 events using Nestle with 64 live points. Resulting plots of the difference between the reconstructed momenta and the truth-level momenta from the data set are shown in Figure 8. The majority of the events are contained in the bins around the mean, which shows the method works considerably well. Summary statistics are displayed, which come from Gaussian fits to the data. The plots of the z momentum have much larger variances due to the lack of constraint in the longitudinal dimension. A plot of the evidences for the signal and background case can be found in Figure 9, which serves as a discriminating variable.

Correlation plots for the neutrino momenta were produced for the correct permutation and for the permutation where the b -jets originating from top decays are switched – an example is shown in Figure 10. This permutation is important to check, as events where two b -jets lie on the Higgs resonance are very rare, meaning they can be easily identified in a signal event, so it remains to permute the last two jets in identifying the correct order of outgoing jets. The plot shows that Nestle performs very well in the correct case, and poorly in the switched case, which is a promising result.

4.3 PolyChord

4.3.1 Theory

POLYCHORD is the most recent and most advanced implementation of NS that was used for this project, which combines ideas from other implementations in order to deal with different situations [22, 23]. It uses an adaption of method known as slice sampling [24], which was first shown to be effective in NS in

Figure 8: Plots of output from Nestle analysis of the difference between reconstructed and true neutrino momenta for 10000 events from the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV signal data set. Summary statistics are displayed, which come from Gaussian fits to the data.

Figure 9: Plot of $\log Z$ for $t\bar{t}h$ signal events and $t\bar{t}b\bar{b}$ background events taken from data samples at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. The numbering on the vertical axis is omitted, as the plot serves just to demonstrate separation, which can be gauged by eye using the amount of non-overlapping area.

Figure 10: Correlation plot of reconstructed ν_x against true ν_x on the correct and switched b -jet from top-decay permutations for output from Nestle analysis of 10000 events from the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV signal data set.

application to systems biology [25]. This works by first choosing a “slice” of probability P_0 uniformly from the interval $[0, P_{max}]$, where P_{max} is the maximum posterior probability. Sampling is then done in the region of θ for which $\mathcal{L}(\theta|\mathbf{x}) > P_0$, similar to the sampling within iso-likelihood contours of increasing likelihood found in the original algorithm by Skilling.

POLYCHORD has a nice Python interface to the FORTRAN backend it was originally written in, which was used for this project. Run-time settings like the number of live points, whether to output samples, number of slices per iteration etc. are contained in a single `settings.py` file, which proved very useful when wanting to retain the same settings across multiple runs that is needed when sampling over multiple events. POLYCHORD also uses a prior transform in a similar way to Nestle.

Output in POLYCHORD is currently managed through the use of `.txt` files, which doesn’t scale well in terms of file size with the volume of analyses performed in the case of this project. This is a known fault in the program, and remains an open problem. Future work on this project would involve preferentially outputting the posterior samples and $\log Z$ values as `.numpy` objects, which exist for each set of runs over multiple events¹.

4.3.2 Results

Installation was relatively painless; similar problems were found to that of the DIAMONDS installation, however these were quickly resolved. The Python code to calculate the MEM integrand was adapted from the Nestle implementation in order to link and run POLYCHORD functions, with the same prior transform being used as in the Nestle analysis. Code was written to extract, analyse, and plot the output samples for each variable, along with the corresponding evidence values. Analysis was initially tested with 64 live points on the correct and switched permutations for 722 events from the signal data set in order to see how well the method distinguishes them. A plot of $\log Z$ showing separation between the correct and switched permutations is shown in Figure 11. One can see by eye that there is a considerable amount of non-overlapping area, demonstrating clear discrimination in spite of the relatively small set of data.

It is illustrative to see the correlation plots for the neutrino momenta in $(0, 1)$, as this spans the whole range of possible momenta. In order to produce these plots, an inverse mapping to the prior transform needed to be constructed to make the truth-level momentum values comparable to the output from NS. With a small amount of algebra, one can invert the previous transform for truth-level momenta $z_t \in (-\infty, \infty)$ back to $u \in (0, 1)$ with the map

¹Dr Pat Scott of the GAMBIT collaboration has advised that the output will be managed much better in the next version of POLYCHORD.

Figure 11: Histogram of $\log Z$ taken from a run of 722 events for output from POLYCHORD analysis on the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV signal data set, showing separation between the correct and switched permutations of outgoing b -jets. Gaussian error bars on each bin are displayed.

$$u = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 + 4z_t^2} - a + 2z_t}{4z_t}, \quad (6)$$

where a is defined as before. Correlation plots for the neutrino three-momentum in the case of the correct and switched permutations are shown in Figure 12. As implied by the good separation in Figure 11, the plots from analysis of the correct permutation of outgoing b -jets show good correlation, whether as the permutation where the jets from top decays are swapped shows poor results. The gaps in the centre of some of the plots are due to the nature of the mapping to $(0, 1)$.

After these plots were made, it was intended to run the algorithm over all permutations of outgoing objects for 10000 events of a newly produced ATLAS Monte Carlo sample that took into account detector smearing. However, the runs ran into some unexpected problems, such as a lack of disk space and repeated bus errors. As a result, the correlation and evidence plots for the 722 events in the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV signal data set are the final results obtained within the time-span of this project.

4.4 Other implementations

Other implementations of NS were explored, but were unsuccessful in being immediately useful in the application to the MEM.

DNest4 was the first of these; installation was incredibly quick and the sampling interface intuitive, but it required the user to implement a class for their likelihood derived from a base class. This in principle is fine, but it contained methods that needed overriding that didn't interface with any of our MEM implementations very well. It is possible to use this sampler based on the existing code, but in-depth study of the intricacies of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm is needed to do so in order to correctly implement this class.

The other software implementation of NS that was looked at was MULTINEST. This was a little tricky to set up, but even when it was eventually working, the sampling efficiency was very poor, with the number of samples being very small compared to the number of dead points and likelihood evaluations.

Figure 12: Correlation plots of reconstructed ν momentum values against the corresponding truth-level values mapped to $(0, 1)$ for output from POLYCHORD analysis on 722 events from the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV signal data set. The upper plot is from the analysis using the correct permutation of outgoing b -jets, and the lower plot comes from analysis on the permutation where the jets from top decays are swapped. Colour scales are omitted as this was intended to be a preliminary test plot. However, it was not possible to perform further analysis due to computational issues and the loss of the data.

5 Discussion & Extensions

Results from Nestle and POLYCHORD are promising upon first glance, showing good correlation between the statistically reconstructed neutrino momenta and their corresponding values at truth level. However, the results presented here are without detector smearing, which was accounted for in a simulated data file that was intended to be analysed. Unfortunately, this was not possible due to unforeseen computational errors². Extensions to this project would include analysis over this data file, and eventually on ATLAS run 2 data. Going further still would involve using full event reconstruction to precisely calculate the top quark Yukawa coupling to the Higgs boson.

The biggest shortcoming of this method is the computational cost. Analysis speeds per permutation were $\approx 42s$ for nestle, and $\approx 140s$ for POLYCHORD. These speeds scale very poorly over the whole data set. The reason for the $> 3\times$ speed difference between the two is that POLYCHORD relies a lot more on MCMC techniques, which are costly at low dimensions³. Additionally, POLYCHORD naturally encodes the ability to parallelise NS with OpenMPI, which was not taken advantage of in this project. Setting this up would be a natural extension of this project, along with potentially installing the recently developed DYPOLYCHORD that uses an improved algorithm known as dynamic nested sampling [26]. It is believed that some routines in MadGraph and numpy may already be using parallelisation, so one would have to tread carefully when trying to run the whole algorithm in parallel to make sure threads don't desynchronise.

5.1 MCMC extensions

A number of MCMC techniques could be used for parameter estimation in application to neutrino reconstruction. Moreover, it is a possible extension of this work to modify the sampling section of the NS algorithm to use some of these methods in order to improve sampling efficiency and reduce computation time.

A recent MCMC algorithm that has shown to work effectively is Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) [27]. This method involves mapping the probability distributions to equivalent quantities of a dynamical system governed by Hamilton's equations. One can then undergo a random walk in parameter/momentum space using algorithms such as the leapfrog method [28]. For kinetic energy K , potential energy U , parameters q , conjugate momenta p , and mass matrix M , the algorithm works like so:

```
initialise vector of parameters  $q_0$ 
for  $i = 1$  to  $i = n$  do
  draw  $p_i$  from multivariate normal distribution with mean 0 and covariance matrix  $M$ 
  using leapfrog method (or similar), simulate dynamics with  $q_{i-1}, p_i$  and propose  $q^*, p^*$ 
  calculate  $\alpha = \min\{\exp\{U(q_{i-1}) - U(q^*) + K(p_i) - K(p^*)\}, 1\}$ 
   $q_i, p_{i+1} = q^*, p^*$  with probability  $\alpha$  or  $q_i, p_{i+1} = q_{i-1}, p_i$  with probability  $1 - \alpha$ 
end for
```

The method's success comes from its ability to exploit the geometry of the system in order to move through it efficiently, though it has multiple parameters that need to be tuned in order to establish conservative Hamiltonian dynamics, something which is required for the method to be effective. A cartoon-style comparison of how HMC explores the posterior compared to a Metropolis random walk is shown in Figure 13. A more complete conceptual introduction to the material is given in [29].

Another technique that could be investigated is approximate Bayesian computation (ABC). One of the attractive features of ABC is that it never explicitly evaluates the likelihood function, which is by far the biggest shortcoming of using the MEM with NS due to its computationally intensive nature. A standard ABC algorithm iteration for distance function $d(\cdot, \cdot)$, data x , and tolerance parameter $\epsilon > 0$ is as follows:

²This analysis was done successfully with Nestle in the end – see [21].

³It is foreseen that speed improvements at low dimensions will take effect in POLYCHORD 2.0.

Figure 13: A cartoon illustration of the comparison between random walk Metropolis and HMC in exploring the posterior distribution, which is indicated using a teal ellipse.

```

draw parameters  $\theta$  from prior  $\pi(\theta)$ 
simulate new data  $x^*$  using  $\theta$ 
calculate sufficient statistic  $S(x^*)$ 
if  $d(S(x), S(x^*)) \leq \epsilon$  then
    accept  $\theta$  as an observation from the posterior  $\pi(\theta|x^*)$ 
else
    reject  $\theta$ 
end if

```

One needs to carefully tune ϵ and choose a suitable form for $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ in order to have a fair sampling efficiency. A standard form for d is a weighted euclidean norm

$$d(x, x^*) = \sum_i \sqrt{\frac{(x_i^*)^2 - x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2}} \quad (7)$$

with tuned weight parameters σ_i . More information on this algorithm can be found in [30].

6 Conclusion

Bayesian inference was successfully applied to the reconstruction of neutrino momenta in $t\bar{t}h$ events by using the Matrix Element Method to define a likelihood function for use in nested sampling. A number of implementations of nested sampling were explored, each with their own strengths and weaknesses. Preliminary plots created using the nested sampling implementations POLYCHORD and Nestle demonstrate good correlation between reconstructed neutrino momenta and the momentum values at truth level. This correlation was significantly worse when the permutation of outgoing b -jets from top quark decay were switched. Clear separation between the correct and switched permutations is found by examining the values of the Bayesian evidence Z .

The method has the large drawback of repeated evaluations of the likelihood function, which incurs a high computational load due to the nature of calculating scattering cross-sections. This could be alleviated by incorporating the natural parallelisation capabilities of the algorithms, along with using advanced Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques to sample the prior distributions efficiently. The modular nature of the code produced allows for easy future application to other similar problems.

References

- [1] Ian Connelly. *A search for the Higgs boson decaying to two b-quarks in association with a dileptonically decaying top-quark pair with the ATLAS detector*. PhD thesis, Royal Holloway, University of London, 2016.
- [2] Olaf Nackenhorst. *Search for the Standard Model Higgs boson produced in association with tt and decaying into bb at 8 TeV with the ATLAS detector using the Matrix Element Method*. PhD thesis, Göttingen Universität, 2015.
- [3] Bezrukov, F. Why should we care about the top quark Yukawa coupling? *J.Exp.Theor.Phys.* 120, 2015.
- [4] John Skilling et al. Nested sampling for general Bayesian computation. *Bayesian analysis*, 1(4):833–859, 2006.
- [5] DØ Collaboration. Observation of the Top quark. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 74, 1995.
- [6] CDF Collaboration. Observation of Top quark Production in $p\bar{p}$ Collision with Collider Detector at Fermilab. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 74, 1995.
- [7] Georges Aad et al. Observation of a new particle in the search for the Standard Model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC. *Phys. Lett.*, B716:1–29, 2012.
- [8] C. Patrignani et al. (Particle Data Group). Review of Particle Physics. *Chinese Physics C*, 2017.
- [9] N.D. Simpson. Development of the Matrix Element Method in Application to Dileptonic ttH Processes. 2018.
- [10] E Fermi. *Nuclear Physics*. University of Chicago Press, 1950.
- [11] ATLAS Collaboration. The ATLAS Experiment at the CERN Large Hadron Collider, journal = Journal of Instrumentation Vol. 3, year = 2008.
- [12] Handley, W. PolyChord: Next Generation Nested Sampling - Sampling, Parameter Estimation and Bayesian Model Comparison. http://www.mpe.mpg.de/~aws/polychord_garching.pdf. Accessed 08/05/2018.
- [13] Brendon J. Brewer and Daniel Foreman-Mackey. DNest4: Diffusive Nested Sampling in C++ and Python. 2016.
- [14] E. Corsaro and J. De Ridder. DIAMONDS: a new Bayesian nested sampling tool. In *European Physical Journal Web of Conferences*, volume 101 of *European Physical Journal Web of Conferences*, page 06019, September 2015.
- [15] DIAMONDS GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/JorisDeRidder/DIAMONDS/blob/master/>. Accessed 02/05/2018.
- [16] Dau Pelleg and Andrew Moore. X-means: Extending k-means with efficient estimation of the number of clusters. In *In Proceedings of the 17th International Conf. on Machine Learning*, pages 727–734. Morgan Kaufmann, 2000.
- [17] Doug Schouten, Adam DeAbreu, and Bernd Stelzer. Accelerated Matrix Element Method with Parallel Computing. *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, 192:54–59, 2015.
- [18] H. Murayama, I. Watanabe, and Kaoru Hagiwara. HELAS: HELicity amplitude subroutines for Feynman diagram evaluations. 1992.
- [19] Nestle GitHub Repository. <https://github.com/kbarbary/nestle>. Accessed 02/05/2018.
- [20] F. Feroz, M. P. Hobson, and M. Bridges. Multinest: an efficient and robust bayesian inference tool for cosmology and particle physics. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 398(4):1601–1614, 2009.
- [21] R. Tombs. Semester 2 MPhys Report (title unknown). 2018.
- [22] W. J. Handley, M. P. Hobson, and A. N. Lasenby. PolyChord: nested sampling for cosmology. *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.*, 450(1):L61–L65, 2015.
- [23] W. J. Handley, M. P. Hobson, and A. N. Lasenby. POLYCHORD: next-generation nested sampling. , 453:4384–4398, November 2015.
- [24] Radford M. Neal. Slice sampling. *Ann. Statist.*, 31(3):705–767, 06 2003.
- [25] Stuart Aitken and Ozgur E. Akman. Nested sampling for parameter inference in systems biology: application to an exemplar circadian model. *BMC Systems Biology*, 7(1):72, Jul 2013.
- [26] Edward Higson, Will Handley, Mike Hobson, and Anthony Lasenby. Dynamic nested sampling: an improved algorithm for parameter estimation and \rightarrow evidence calculation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.03459*, 2017.
- [27] R. M. Neal. MCMC using Hamiltonian dynamics. *ArXiv e-prints*, June 2012.
- [28] Ernst Hairer and Christian Lubich. Long-term analysis of the störmer—verlet method for hamiltonian systems with a solution-dependent high frequency. *Numer. Math.*, 134(1):119–138, September 2016.
- [29] M. Betancourt. A Conceptual Introduction to Hamiltonian Monte Carlo. *ArXiv e-prints*, January 2017.
- [30] S. A. Sisson, Y. Fan, and M. A. Beaumont. Overview of Approximate Bayesian Computation. *ArXiv e-prints*, February 2018.